

DEVELOPMENT OF SAMBO: HISTORY AND TODAY

Tashkent Region, Qibray District

Lecturer of the Department of

Physical Education and Sports of Agrarian University

Rakhmanov Boburbek Oybekovich

Independent researcher

Annotation: This article covers important information about the development of sambo as a sport. Moreover, historical background of sambo and its peculiarities of modern world were discussed.

Key words: *self-defence systems, "rehabilitated", cross-pollinated, Sambo wrestling, official tournament, sambo championship, Concrete Sambo, Beach Sambo.*

Sambo is a martial art and combat sport developed and used by the Soviet Red Army in the early 1920s to improve their hand-to-hand combat abilities. The sport is similar in many ways to judo and jujutsu but also incorporates different types of wrestling and various self-defence systems. The name "SAMBO" derives from the Russian acronym SAMozashchita Bez Oruzhiya, which literally means "self-defence without weapons". Soviet martial arts expert Vasili Oshchepkov is credited as one of the founding fathers of Sambo. Born into a family of exiles in 1893, Oshchepkov also played a key role in introducing judo into the Soviet Union.

An intelligence officer during both Tsarist and Soviet periods, he was educated in Japan and later returned there to work in the 1920s. He studied at the Kodokan Judo Institute in Tokyo, founded by Jigoro Kano, and eventually

became the first Russian to receive a second dan in the sport. This led to him developing the SAMBO self-defence techniques which were developed and utilised by the Soviet Red Army and intelligence services. Oshchepkov, despite his important legacy, ultimately died in prison aged just 45 as a result of the Stalinist political purges of 1937 after accusations of being a Japanese spy. He was posthumously "rehabilitated" and cleared of wrongdoing in 1957. Viktor Spiridonov and Anatoly Kharlampiev, a student of Oshchepkov, are also considered pioneers of SAMBO. Spiridonov and Oshchepkov independently developed two different styles, which eventually cross-pollinated and became what is known as SAMBO.

There are multiple competitive sport variations of sambo (though sambo techniques and principles can be applied to many other combat sports). Below are the main formats that are recognized by FIAS.

1. Sport sambo or Sambo wrestling is stylistically similar to old-time judo, and in a lot of ways influenced by it, but with some differences in rules, protocol, and uniform. Sambo allows various types of leg locks like old Judo before the ban of the Ashi Garami techniques, while not allowing chokeholds. It also focuses on throwing, groundwork, and submissions, with very few restrictions on gripping and holds. Sambo is an international style of amateur wrestling recognized by the FILA (now UWW) Congress in 1966.
2. Combat sambo (Russian: Боевое Самбо, romanized: Boyevoye Sambo). Utilized and developed for the military, combat sambo resembles modern mixed martial arts, including forms of striking and grappling. Combat sambo allows regular punches, kicks, elbows, and knees, as well as soccer kicks, headbutts and groin strikes, in addition to throws, holds, chokes and locks, except for a standing or flying wristbar. The chief distinction from Brazilian jiu-jitsu (BJJ), apart from striking techniques, is that combat sambo rules and regulations do not permit a one-sided resort

to ground fighting without throws or other combative manoeuvres (i.e., by simply sitting down and continuing from the ground without touching his opponent that BJJ allows). In terms of aliveness, combat sambo surpasses ARB by design, though both were designed for combat situations only. Competitors wear jackets as in sport sambo, but also hand protection and sometimes shin protection and headgear. The first FIAS World Combat Sambo Championships were held in 2001. The World Combat Sambo Federation, based in Russia, also sanctions international combat sambo events. Combat sambo is designed to tackle certain tasks. The effectiveness of this martial art determined by its structure, namely by three components: boxing, sambo, and adapters. Adapters of combat sambo were developed by the academician G. S. Popov. The task of adapters is to ensure the safe transition from middle distance to close one, as well as the consistent usage of sambo and boxing techniques. The given configuration provides the fusion of two martial arts into a single system[2]. Women participated in Combat Sambo for the first time in an official tournament in the Paris Grand Prix 2015. The first recognized instance of women competing in an international combat Sambo tournament was in the 2022 Asian and Oceania Sambo Championships. In 2022, Australia and New Zealand competed for the first time in the Asian sambo championship.

3. Freestyle Sambo- This type of Sambo was introduced by the American Sambo Association in 2004. Its purpose was to encourage non-Sambo practitioners such as Judo and Jiu-Jitsu to participate in Sambo. Freestyle Sambo allows the use of chokeholds and other submission techniques that are not used in Sambo wrestling.
4. FCF-MMA- This was developed in 2003 as a form of Sambo without competing in the traditional uniform of Kurtka (jacket), shorts and boots. Competitors just wear fight shorts and gloves. One competitor wears blue

and the other red, the same as traditional Sambo. Matches are held on a traditional wrestling mat, not in a cage or ring like normal MMA fights. Techniques from all martial arts are used to defeat an opponent by knock out, submission or point victory.

5. Self-Defence Sambo- This kind of Sambo is about defending oneself. In it, practitioners are taught to guard against weapons. Most of the moves that are taught include using the attacker's aggression against them, which is similar to what is done in both Jiu-Jitsu and Aikido. Spiridonov's influence is strong in this style of Sambo.
6. Concrete Sambo- This type of Sambo was made for the Argentinian Army during the military dictatorship. It is similar to special sambo in terms of origin and uses.
7. Special Sambo- This type of Sambo was made for Army Special Forces and other rapid response forces. It is only designed for the particular group that uses it. In that sense, it's similar to sambo combat, which is also designed for a specific purpose.
8. Beach Sambo- Sambo beach, as the name suggests, is held on soft beaches or strips of sand.
9. Derivatives of sambo- Systema (or System) is also known as "Combat Sambo Spetsnaz". This Russian martial art is the evolutionary form of Spiridonov's Samoz. Systema falls into the category of military Sambo. The evolution of Spiridonov's Samoz and Ochtchepkov's Sambo was maintained in parallel by the NKVD which itself became the KGB.

It is out of the official path of the evolution of Military and Sports Sambo that Systema was created, even if the latter is based on similar bases to Sambo. The Systema design has been designed to be highly adaptable and practical. It uses breathing exercises, "drills" and "sparring" exercises to replace traditional kata. Because it is open and scalable in nature, Systema is very effective in many

situations and against many fighting styles. This is also why the special units, the spetsnaz, are trained in Systema. There are two major streams of Systema; one more "flexible", the other more "hard".

The vast majority of countries that develop Sambo have the national federations that are members of the FIAS. They receive comprehensive support from our organization, and the recognition of all national federations by the National Olympic Committees of their countries is one of the main priorities of the FIAS work today. More than 30 major SAMBO competitions are held annually at the international level under the auspices of FIAS. The most important of them are the World Cup and the World Championship among boys and girls, junior boys and girls. In addition, Sambo is included in the official program of the World Combat Games "SportAccord", as well as in the Asian Games. In 2013, the Sambo tournament was held in the program of the World Summer Universiade in Kazan, and in 2015 - in the program of the First European Games in Baku[3].

In 1968, FILA accepted sambo as the third style of international wrestling. In 1985, the sambo community formed its own organization, Federation International Amateur Sambo (FIAS). In 1993, FIAS split into two organizations, both of which used the same name and logo, and the two groups were often referred to as FIAS "East" (under Russian control) and FIAS "West" (under US and Western European control). This split mirrored the last days of Cold War politics of the time as well as the recent break-up of the Soviet Union. In the U.S., disagreements between the sport's organizers and the rise of Brazilian Jiu-Jitsu in the 1990s slowed down the growth of sambo before the success of several sambo fighters increased its popularity a decade later. In 2005, FILA reached an agreement with FIAS "West" and re-assumed sanctioning over sport sambo. However, in 2008, FILA again discontinued sanctioning sambo and sambo is now notably missing from the UWW website. At present, only FIAS sanctions international competition in sport sambo. In 2014 FIAS and FILA

signed a cooperative agreement. While this does not place sambo back on UWW's recognized list, it does move towards unity and prevents future 'turf wars' regarding the sport's promotion. A similar agreement was signed by FIAS and the International Judo Federation in 2014 as well.

Both FIAS and the World Combat Sambo Federation host international combat sambo competition. The American Sambo Association has continued to host freestyle sambo tournaments in the US and Canada since 2004. These events are unrecognized by UWW. Rumours rising in 2012 stating that sambo will be included as a demonstration sport in the 2016 Olympics are therefore not supported by any facts, and thus sambo is still a very long way from maturing into an Olympic sport, notwithstanding the effort that is being put into the matter. Indeed, given the intention of the Olympic Committee to remove classic wrestling from the Olympic roster, there are rumours that sambo is highly unlikely to ever make it to the Olympics. However, sambo has been included in the 27th Annual Summer Universiade for the first time in history. FIAS submitted an application to the International Olympic Committee (IOC) to consider sambo for the 2020 Games and has devoted 2010–2013 to creating a sambo commission in the International Sports Press Association (AIPS). As of 30 November 2018, sambo has indeed received temporary recognition by the IOC[4]. This close relationship is reestablishing the global popularity and media emphasis on sambo.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that sports are a crucial part of a student's growth and development. They help in the development of mental health and physical fitness of the body. Through participation in sports and games, a student gains various skills, experience and confidence that are helpful for developing their personality. Sports are very essential for every human life which keeps them fit and fine and physical strength. It has great importance in each stage of life. It also improves the personality of people. Sports keep our all organs alert and our hearts become stronger by regularly playing some kind of

sports. sports has always given priority from old ages and nowadays it has become more fascinating. Due to the physical activity blood pressure also remains healthy, and blood vessels remain clean. Sugar level also reduces and cholesterol comes down by daily activity. Different people have different interests in sports but the action is the same in all sports. Sports are becoming big channels to make more capital/money day by day and the number of people is also increasing. By playing sports even at a young age you can also be better and free from some diseases. By playing sports lung function also improves and becomes healthy because more oxygen is supplied. Sports also improves bone strength even in old age.

REFERENCES:

1. <https://www.insidethegames.biz/articles/1045459/what-is-sambo#:~:text=SAMBO%20is%20a%20martial%20art,and%20various%20self%2Ddefence%20systems>.
2. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sambo_\(martial_art\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sambo_(martial_art))
3. <https://sambo.sport/en/fias/about/>
4. "The International Sambo Federation (FIAS)". Sambo-fias.org. 17 April 2013. Archived from the original on 5 July 2013. Retrieved 18 September 2013.